

TRENDS IN CROPPING PATTERN OF RAYALASEEMA REGION: 1956-57 to 2020-21

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ABSTRACT

Cropping pattern indicates the share of area under various crops at a particular time. The change in cropping pattern during particular period clearly indicates the changes that have taken place in the agricultural development. It is difficult to predict the possible shifts in cropping pattern. Yet, certain possible trends in crop shifts can be seen. Hence, the present paper examined trends in cropping pattern in Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh state during the period between 1956-57 and 2020-21. Some remarkable shifts in cropping pattern have taken place in Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh. The area under food crops especially cereals declined while that of non food crops gained. High value crops including plantations, fruits, vegetables, some oil seeds and horticultural crops have expanded their share over time. In general, the demand for cereals and millets is falling on account of a reduction in the caloric requirements due to more sedentary ways of life than earlier all social classes and more and more diversified food baskets with implicit substitution of cereals and millets by pulses, edible oils, milk and milk products, fruits and vegetables eggs and chicken, meat, fish etc.

Key Words: Cropping Pattern, Food Crops, Cereals, Pulses, Oil Seeds, Fruits and Vegetables, Rayalaseema, Gross Cropped Area.

1. Introduction

The state of Andhra Pradesh has witnessed gradual diversification of the agricultural sector over a period of time. The nature of this transformation was a shift in traditional agriculture to commercial agriculture. Even though the cash crops experienced high volatility due to consecutive droughts and decelerating crop yields and price fluctuations, crop shifts has been continuing towards high value crops. High value crops performed impressively and rescued the

agriculture sector to a great extent. Agricultural sector in Rayalaseema has also moved from a traditional agriculture in the 1950s to the modern technologically dynamic high capital intensive agriculture, in which along with food and non-food crops, horticulture and other allied activities have also expanded. In this context, the present paper aimed to know the crop shifts in Rayalaseema region of Andhra Pradesh with the following objectives.

2. Objectives

- 1.To study the changes in Area under Food and Non Food Crops in Rayalaseema Region from 1956-57 to 2020-21
2. To analyse the trends in Area under Food and Non Food Crops across Districts in Rayalaseema Region
3. To examine the changes in area under different crops in Rayalaseema during the period between 1960-61 and 2020-21.

3. Methodology

This Study is based on secondary data only. Secondary data is collected from both the published and unpublished sources. The main published sources are Statistical Abstracts, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Hyderabad, Statistical Abstracts, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Amaravati, AP. The unpublished sources are Ph.Ds. and M.Phil Dissertations and unpublished information from Agricultural departments. The secondary data is also collected for during the last seven decades.

4. Profile of Rayalaseema Region

Rayalaseema Region is located in the state of Andhra Pradesh at the heart of Deccan plateau (in South India) is arid, semi-arid and chronically drought-prone for centuries. This backward region has a dubious distinction for twin problems of drought and poverty. It is the second most driest region in India after Rajasthan. This geo-political region consists of 4 districts i.e., Anantapur, Kadapa, Chittoor and Kurnool. The region has a geographical area of approx 67.29 lakh ha. and has a population of 130 Lakhs. The cultivated area is 24.16 lakh ha. of which only 5.57 lakh ha 23% area is irrigated with underground water and some river water. It has 14.9 lakh ha. (22%)

under forest land mostly without tree cover. The groundwater irrigation as well as river water irrigation is also undependable in the region. There is very little industry in the region and livelihoods are dependent on mostly rainfed farming which is prone for very frequent droughts. The annual average rainfall in this region ranges from about 350 mm to about 650 mm from both South-West monsoon (from June to September) and North-East monsoon (from October and November). The region consists of predominantly (85%) small and marginal farmers mostly from poor and marginalized communities.

5. Changes in Area under Food and Non Food Crops in Rayalaseema Region

Cropping pattern shows the area under different crops during an particular period i.e agricultural year. The crops mainly classifies as Food Crops and Non Food Crops. Food Crops include Cereals (including Millets), Pulses and Other Food Crops. Rice and Wheat are the important Cereal Crops and Rice is the major staple crop in Andhra Pradesh. Jowar, Bajra, Maize, Ragi, Samai, Korra, Varagu, Bontha, Arukulu, Vooda and Anumu are the important Millet Crops. Major Pulses crops are Horsegram, Greengram, Blackgram, Redgram, Bengalgram, Cowgram, Rajma Beans, Anumulu and Erra Pappu (Mysore Pappu). Other Food Crops are like Condiments & Spices, Sugarcane, Vegetables and Fruits. Non Food Crops constitute Fibres, Oil Seeds, Pulp & Timber, Drugs and Narcotics, Fodder Crops, Green Manure Crops, Aromatic Plants, Flowers and Others.

Changes in the area under food and non food crops in Rayalaseema region is presented in this table. It is observed from the table 1 that Gross cropped area has been fluctuating during the last seven decades in Rayalaseema region. Gross cropped area declined continuously during the first four decades i.e 1956 to 1981. There after it increased from between 1991 and 2011. Again it has declined during the current decade. The gross cropped area declined from 32.2 lakh hectares in 1956 to 29.2 lakh hectares in 1991. After that it increased from 29.2 lakh hectares to 31.7 lakh hectares by 2011 and again it declined to 26.9 lakh hectares in 2021. Erratic rainfall and climate changes are the reasons for fluctuations in gross cropped area in Rayalaseema region.

With regard to area under food and non food crops in Rayalaseem, their relative shares vary from time to time. The ratio of area under food crops was very significant up to 1980s, while that of

area under non food crops was very low. After that, the area under food crops has been declined while the non food crops area has been rising rapidly. In other words, the demand for non food crops has been increasing after 1980s. The ratio of area under food crops was very high i.e 73.1 % in 1961. After that, the proportion of food crops has been declined to 44.9 % by 2021. In contrast, the ratio of non food crops area has been rising from 26.9 % to 45.1 % during the same time.

Table 1: Trends in Area under Food and Non Food Crops in Rayalaseema Region

Year	Area in Hectares				Gross Cropped Area	%
	Food Crops	%	Non Food Crops	%		
1956-57	2268048	70.2	960973	29.8	3229021	100.0
1960-61	2344173	73.1	861977	26.9	3206150	100.0
1970-71	1959425	62.7	1166087	37.3	3125512	100.0
1980-81	1561456	60.5	1019886	39.5	2581342	100.0
1990-91	1066265	36.5	1857162	63.5	2923427	100.0
2000-01	1132047	37.3	1900813	62.7	3032860	100.0
2010-11	1452961	45.8	1720243	54.2	3173204	100.0
2020-21	1481617	54.9	1215215	45.1	2696832	100.0

Source: 1. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Season and Crop Reports (various years), Government of Andhra Pradesh
2. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Statistical Abstracts (various years), Government of Andhra Pradesh

The total area under food crops drastically declined from 22.6 lakh hectares to 11.3 lakh hectares during the period between 1956 and 2001. But, slightly it increased to 14.8 lakh hectares by 2021 (Table 1). Drastic changes in rainfall and climate in Rayalaseema, low prices of cereals and millets etc. are main reasons for farmers shifted from food to non food crops.

With in the food crops, the data indicates that the area under cereals and millets drastically declined from 19.1 lakh hectares in 1956 to 4.9 lakh hectares by 2021. This decline is about four times. In contrast, the area under pulses and other food crops has been increasing tremendously during the same period. The area under pulses rose from 2.3 lakh hectares to 5.6 lakh hectares and other food crops area gone up from 1.2 lakh hectares to 4.2 lakh hectares during the same period. The growth of area under pulses is more than double and it is more than three times in other food crops.

The proportion of area under cereals and millets, pulses and other food crops was 84.5 percent, 10.1 percent and 5.4 percent respectively. The relative shares changed dramatically after 1980s. After 1981, the share of area under pulses increased from 9.3 percent to 37.9 percent during the period between 1981 and 2021 (Table 2). Similarly, the share of area under other food crops increased from 12.5 percent to 29 percent during the same period.

Table 2 :Area under different Food Crops in Rayalaseema Region

Area in Hectares				
Year	Cereals	Pulses	Other Food Crops	Total Food Crops
1956-57	1916709	230043	121296	2268048
1960-61	2002933	214823	126416	2344173
1970-71	1597197	181490	180738	1959425
1980-81	1221600	145899	193957	1561456
1990-91	694039	155429	216797	1066265
2000-01	536918	255349	339780	1132047
2010-11	485668	607851	359442	1452961
2020-21	490760	562209	428648	1481617
Percentage				
Year	Cereals	Pulses	Other Food Crops	Total Food Crops
1956-57	84.5	10.1	5.4	100.0
1960-61	85.4	9.1	5.5	100.0
1970-71	81.5	9.3	9.2	100.0
1980-81	78.2	9.3	12.5	100.0
1990-91	65.0	14.6	20.4	100.0
2000-01	47.2	22.6	30.2	100.0
2010-11	33.4	41.8	24.8	100.0
2020-21	33.1	37.9	29.0	100.0

Source: 1. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Season and Crop Reports (various years), Government of Andhra Pradesh
 2. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Statistical Abstracts (various years), Government of Andhra Pradesh

6. Changes in Area under different Crops in Rayalaseema

One of the important factors contributing to agricultural growth is the diversification from low value crops to high value and high productivity crops. Changes in the cropping pattern would serve as good indicator of the level of development of agriculture. Traditionally, a cropping pattern dominated by food crops, especially cereals, is supposed to be closer to subsistence agriculture, and diversification away from food crops is a crude indicator of growing commercialization of agriculture. Rayalaseema region in Andhra Pradesh witnessed considerable change in the cropping pattern between 1956 and 2021, when about 70 percent of the cropped area was under food crops and 2020-21, by which time food crops accounted only 45 percent. There has been considerable changes with in the composition of food crops as well as with in the non food crops.

It is observed from the table 3 that the changes in the cropping pattern in Rayalaseema Region during the first 20 years between 1960-61 and 1980-81, were marginal. After 1980s there were dramatic shifts in the cropping pattern. Within the food crops the principal decline has been in the millets. Jowar, which accounted for about 26.7 percent of the total cropped area in 1960-61, had a share of only 1.4 percent in 2020-21 (Table 4). In Rayalaseema, jowar was not only the principal food crop but also the single largest crop accounting for about 6.16 lakh hectares in 1960-61. But by 2020-21, the are came down to just 0.4 lakh hectares. Bajra and Raagi too, after 1980s experienced drastic decline in the area. The area under Bajra and Raagi was declined from 1.29 and 0.89 lakh hectares respectively in 1980-81 to 18.1 and 7.6 thousand hectares by 2020-21. Maize is another cereal crop that witnessed an dramatic increase in the area in recent decades. The area under maize was only 3 to 5 thousand hectares between 1960-61 to 2000-02. There after it has increased to 1.1 lakh hectares by 2020-21.

Another group of food crops , which showed positive gain, is pulses. Of course, there were intra-group differences in the gains or lossess of area. In 1960-61, horsegram was the principal pulse crop in the Rayalaseema Region, occupying highest area (1.36 lakh hectares) among pulse crops. But, by 2020-21 this crop declined drastically to a very insignificantly low area (0.14 lakh hectares). The area under Bengal gram registered a significant increase after 1980s. In 1980-81, the area under Bengalgram was only 0.1 lakh hectares and increased to 3.27 lakh hectares by 2020-21 and presently accounts for the single largest area under pulses in the Rayalaseema

Region followed by Redgram. There was no change in the area under green gram between 1960-61 and 2020-21 in the Region. The area under black gram was no change between 1960-61 and 1980-81 and slightly increased between 1980-81 and 2000-01. Thereafter, it increased significantly from 4 thousand hectares to 64 thousand hectares during the period between 2000-01 to 2020-21.

The area under Oilseeds, especially groundnut has been on the increase. The area under groundnut increased from 5.92 lakh hectares in 1960-61 to 7.79 lakh hectares by 1980-81 and again increased to 14.1 lakh hectares by 2020-21. But, by 2020-21 this crop declined drastically to 7.92 lakh hectares. Sunflower is yet another oilseed crop in this region. There was no sunflower crop in Rayalaseema upto 1980s. But, during the period between 1980s and 2000s this crop that emerged as an important oilseed crop of the Rayalaseema Region. The area under sunflower crop was only 7 hundred hectares in 1980-81. But, by 2000-01, it increased abnormally to more than 2 lakh hectares. However, thereafter, it declined drastically to 0.16 lakh hectares by 2020-21. The area under castor was under decline till 1980s but revived in 2000s.

Cotton is very important crop that emerged as an commercial crop of the Region. The area under this crop was 2.67 lakh hectares in 1960-61. By 1980-81, it declined to 1.41 lakh hectares. There after it rose to 1.65 lakh hectares by 2000-01 and again increased significantly to 4.38 lakh hectares by 2020-21.

The area under vegetables and horticulture crops came down from 2.27 lakhs to 0.73 lakh hectares during the period between 1960-61 and 1980-81. But, by 2000-01 it went up to 1.85 lakh hectares and again it increased significantly to 5.27 lakh hectares by 2020-21.

The percentage of the total cropped area occupied by each crop in the Rayalaseema region from 1961 to 2021. In 1961 shows that the total cropped area was 2311.7 hectares. Jowar was the most commonly sown crop, covering 26.7 percent of the area. Groundnut followed closely, occupying 25.6 percent of the total cropped area. Other millets constituted 23.3 percent, while rice, despite being a staple food, accounted for only 13 percent of the total cropped area. Crops such as maize, Bengal gram, green gram, cow gram, sunflower, tobacco, sugarcane, and castor each accounted for less than 1 percent of the total cropped area, indicating their minimal cultivation.

Table 3: Area and its Share across Crops in Rayalaseema during Different Periods
(Area in '000 hectares)

Crop	1961	%	1981	%	2001	%	2021	%
Rice	300.1	13.0	349.2	13.0	313.7	10.7	296.1	10.2
jowar	616.4	26.7	470.0	17.5	141.3	4.8	40.4	1.4
Bajra	184.5	8.0	129.7	4.8	28.3	1.0	18.1	0.6
Ragi	130.6	5.6	81.7	3.0	19.7	0.7	7.6	0.3
Maize	3.2	0.1	2.0	0.1	5.4	0.2	108.1	3.7
Other Millets	539.7	23.3	344.2	12.8	28.9	1.0	9.7	0.3
Bengalgram	15.2	0.7	10.7	0.4	133.4	4.6	327.4	11.3
Redgram	46.1	2.0	40.1	1.5	85.4	2.9	137.5	4.7
Greengram	10.0	0.4	8.3	0.3	9.6	0.3	5.8	0.2
Blackgram	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	4.0	0.1	64.9	2.2
Horsegram	136.7	5.9	83.4	3.1	9.7	0.3	14.8	0.5
Cowgram	0.5	0.0	0.7	0.0	3.3	0.1	2.3	0.1
Other Fulses	5.3	0.2	4.3	0.2	5.0	0.2	6.5	0.2
Groundnut	592.2	25.6	779.7	29.0	1409.4	48.3	792.2	27.4
Castor	21.4	0.9	8.0	0.3	15.7	0.5	12.4	0.4
Sunflower	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	203.7	7.0	16.9	0.6
Other Oil Seeds	74.9	3.2	105.4	3.9	70.0	2.4	11.7	0.4
Chillies	34.8	1.5	19.0	0.7	25.3	0.9	44.2	1.5
Sugarcane	13.2	0.6	26.7	1.0	41.0	1.4	10.8	0.4
Cotton	267.2	11.6	141.6	5.3	165.3	5.7	438.8	15.1
Tobacco	7.9	0.3	10.0	0.4	16.7	0.6	2.9	0.1
Fruits&Veg	227.3	9.8	73.0	2.7	185.0	6.3	527.3	18.2
Total Cropped Area	2311.7	100.0	2689.4	100.0	2919.8	100.0	2896.4	100.0

Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Statistical Abstracts (various years), Government of Andhra Pradesh

By 1981, groundnut's share increased to 29 percent, making it the crop with the largest cropped area. Jowar saw a significant decrease to 17.5 percent, falling to second place. Rice maintained its share at 13 percent. Other millets also experienced a notable decline, dropping to 12.8 percent. Crops like maize, Bengal gram, green gram, cow gram, sunflower, tobacco, sugarcane, and castor still each accounted for less than 1 percent of the total cropped area.

In 2001, the total cropped area increased to 2919.8 hectares. Groundnut emerged as the predominant cash crop for Rayalaseema farmers, covering 48 percent of the total cropped area. This dominance led to a sharp decline in the cropped area for other crops. Rice was the second most cultivated crop, accounting for 10.7 percent of the total cropped area. Sunflower had a surprising jump from 0 percent to 7 percent in two decades. Some of the previously neglected crops saw a slight increase in their share.

By 2021, the cropping pattern had diversified, with more crops having a significant share of the total cropped area. The total cropped area slightly decreased to 2896.4 hectares. Groundnut remained highly cultivated but its share declined to 27.4 percent. Fruits and vegetables saw a substantial increase from 6.3 percent in 2001 to 18.2 percent in 2021. Cotton also increased significantly, from 5.7 percent to 15 percent over the same period. Rice saw a minor decrease in its share from 10.7 percent to 10.2 percent. Bengal gram's share increased from 4.6 percent to around 11 percent. Additionally, red gram and horse gram consistently increased their share over the past sixty years.

7. Growth Rates for Different Crops in Rayalaseema for different periods

Table 3 presents the growth trends of various crops in the Rayalaseema region over six decades, from 1961 to 2021. The total cropped area increased by 0.38 percent over this period, but recorded a negative growth rate of -0.04 percent from 2001 to 2021. While many crops increased their absolute cropped area and share of the total cropped area, most did not experience significant growth. In fact, many saw negative growth rates.

The crop with the highest growth over the past sixty years was not one of the commonly sown crops. Black gram, which accounted for 2 percent of the total cropped area in 2021, had an impressive growth rate of 7.2 percent. It started from 0 percent, grew by 7 percent by 2001, and then by 14 percent until 2021. This rate effectively doubled every two decades.

Maize also saw substantial growth, with an overall rate of 6 percent. The significant increase occurred in the past two decades (2001-2021), during which it grew by 16.16 percent. Groundnut, despite being the most sown crop, saw only a modest growth rate of 0.49 percent. This limited growth was primarily due to a decline in the past twenty years, reflecting a shift in farmers' crop choices and consumer demand. Fruits and vegetables recorded a positive growth

rate of 1.41 percent. They recovered from an initial negative growth during 1961-1981, showing steady increases from 1981 to 2021. Cotton also grew significantly from 2001 to 2021, with a growth rate of 5 percent. Overall, cotton's growth rate from 1961 to 2021 was 0.83 percent. Cow gram experienced a decline in growth during the period 2001-2021, which reduced its overall growth rate to 2.58 percent.

Table Growth Rates for Different Crops in Rayalaseema for different periods

Crop	1961-1981	1981-2001	2001-2021	1961-2021
Rice	0.76	-0.53	-0.29	-0.02
Jowar	-1.35	-5.83	-6.07	-4.44
Bajra	-1.75	-7.33	-2.21	-3.80
Ragi	-2.32	-6.87	-4.65	-4.63
Maize	-2.32	5.09	16.16	6.04
Other Millets	-2.22	-11.65	-5.31	-6.48
Bengalgram	-1.74	13.45	4.59	5.25
Redgram	-0.69	3.85	2.41	1.84
Greengram	-0.93	0.73	-2.49	-0.90
Blackgram	0.00	7.18	14.95	7.20
Horsegram	-2.44	-10.20	2.13	-3.64
Cowgram	1.70	8.06	-1.79	2.58
Other Pulses	-1.04	0.76	1.32	0.34
Groundnut	1.38	3.00	-2.84	0.49
Castor	-4.80	3.43	-1.17	-0.91
Sunflower	0	32.80	-11.70	-
Other Oil Seeds	1.72	-2.03	-8.56	-3.05
Chillies	-2.98	1.44	2.83	0.40
Sugarcane	3.58	2.17	-6.45	-0.33
Cotton	-3.13	0.78	5.00	0.83
Tobacco	1.19	2.60	-8.38	-1.66
Fruits &Vegetables	-5.52	4.76	5.38	1.41
Total Cropped Area	0.76	0.76	0.04	0.38

Bengal gram has grown extensively at 13 percent during the period 1981-2001 but right after recorded a decline to 4.59 percent in 2001-2021. It's growth rate during the entire study period is 5.25 percent. Most of the commonly sown crops like Rice, Jowar, Bajra, Ragi, Other Millets, and Tobacco had a negative growth during 1981-2001 and 2001-2021 and hence pushing their growth for the hole of the study period into negative.

These growth trends highlight the dynamic changes in cropping patterns in Rayalaseema over the past six decades, influenced by shifts in farmer preferences and consumer demand.

8. Conclusion

The changes in the cropping pattern in Rayalaseema Region suggest that wherever agroclimatic conditions permit, the farmers of the region have been constantly trying to switch from low value crops to high value crops. Whatever might be the nutritional and other considerations, the area under low value cereal and millets have drastically come down. The substituting crops that gained are mainly pulses and horticulture crops. This shift in cropping patterns reflects a significant change in the choices made by farmers, with a noticeable move towards cultivating more diverse and profitable crops. In coming days, cropping pattern will have to respond not only to changes in domestic consumer demand, but also to international demand.

References

- Government of Andhra Pradesh : Statistical Abstract of Andhra Pradesh (Various years), Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Hyderabad.
- Government of Andhra Pradesh : Statistical Abstract of Andhra Pradesh (Various years), Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Amaravathi.
- Government of Andhra Pradesh : Season and Crop Reports (Various years), Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Amaravathi.
- Lakshmi, S.B.R and Devi, I.B. 2012. Crop shifts in coastal region of Andhra Pradesh: A markov chain approach. *Agricultural Situation in India*, 69(7).
- Mohan G (2017) Determinants of Cropping Pattern Changes in Andhra Pradesh, India. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*. 20 (3).
- Ragamalika V, Rajeswari S, Aparna B and Ravindra Reddy B 2021 Crop Shifts in Rayalaseema Region of Andhra Pradesh: A Markov Chain Approach. *Andhra Pradesh Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 5(4).
- Reddy G R, Reddy M C, Pravallika K And Gita B M 2022 Dynamics of Cropping Pattern in Krishna Zone Of Andhra Pradesh-Markov Chain Approach. *The Journal of Research Angra*. 50(1).
- Reddy, D.R and Achoth, L. (2000) Dynamics of the cropping pattern changes in Kerala: A markov chain approach. *Mysore Journal of Agricultural Sciences*,34.